

The Effects of Rural-Urban Migration on The Livelihoods of Migrants: A Case Study of Katima Mulilo (Namibia)

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Abstract

The town of Katima Mulilo is experiencing a rapid growth in rural-urban migration, predominantly in the informal settlements, namely: Makaravani East and West, Choto, Mafuta, Nova, Mahohoma and Lwanyanda. This trend hampers the development agenda of the Katima Mulilo Town Council as the need for basic service is a prerequisite for any developing town. This article looks at the trends of rural-urban migration and its effects on the migrants' livelihoods. The aforementioned would inform relevant stakeholders' planning and decision making in their efforts to manage rural-urban migration, particularly in Katima Mulilo local authority. To understand the dynamics of rural urban-migration, this article adopted a qualitative research method, based on a descriptive and diagnostic research design with a sample of 30 respondents. The thematic data analysis technique was employed to analyse the data. The results revealed that the majority of migrants relocated in the town of Katima Mulilo are looking for employment in a quest to improve their livelihood. This research paper revealed that some of the migrants have access to improved basic service delivery and access to improved public goods i.e., education. Despite the abovementioned reasons, the majority of migrants end up not achieving their planned ambitions. This article recommends for the establishment of long-term commitment and collaboration amongst key stakeholders such as the leadership of both Regional Council and Local Authority in the Zambezi Region (Katima Mulilo). This is crucial in creating an inclusive and equitable environment and guaranteeing the smooth and productive administration of rural-urban migration in Namibia, Katima Mulilo in particular.

Keywords: Livelihood, Migrants, Urban, Rural and Informal settlement.

I. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Mendelson (2017) Explains that Namibia is experiencing a fast shift from a predominantly rural society to an urban-centred one. The shift is most observable in the fast urban growth, particularly in informal settlements, whom the majority are less privileged families who makes their livelihood in shacks. Migration is considered as the movement of individuals from rural to urban areas to look for employment (Moses, Guaping & Ladu, 2017). Migration trends are observed due to an existence of rural-urban inequality in wealth in rural areas.

Since the country's independence in 1990, Katima Mulilo Town Council has experienced a high influx of rural-urban migration and most of the migrants have primarily settled in the informal settlements (Nikanor, 2014). explain that areas exposed to a lack security of land tenure, lacking basic service delivery and infrastructure, lack of housing complinace to that of the building regulations are always characterised as informal settlement in Namibia. Informal settlements have existed for a long time. They became much more widespread with the need for employment opportunities and improved living standards. Thus, informal settlements are considered a rational response to rapid rural-urban migration, which results in poor supply of basic services. Despite other urban centres around Namibia, Windhoek remains the epicentre of rural-urban migration as population continues to grow (Nikanor 2014).

Local authorities have a vast responsibility of addressing the requirements of their inhabitants, particularly emanating from migration (Tacoli, 2015). To ensure the latter, it is fundamental to appreciate the determining factors and implications that come with migration from specific demarcations of an urban area, on the livelihood of the migrants. It is perceived that the reasoning behind migration might not be the same for different migrants in different demarcations of an urban area. "It is necessary for policymakers and planners to know about population movements" (Namibia Statistics Agency, 2019). This process allows policy makers and planners to have the foresight to adequately plan and adopt informed response plans. It is important to note that migration serves as a catalyst in the transformation process, impacting not only the migrants but also the local authorities responsible for service delivery.

I.II. OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this study was to examine the determinants and impact of rural-urban migration on the livelihood of migrants in the Katima Mulilo's informal settlements.

- To determine factors attracting the movement of individuals from rural areas to urban areas in Katima Mulilo.
- To assess the effects of migration on migrants' ability to obtain basic services a
- Identify the demographic characteristics of the migrants.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The review was accomplished by reviewing a wide range of relevant sources with the aim of identify key themes, theories, and practical findings that have shaped the current understanding of the subject matter. Its purpose was to identify any gaps in literature, which would help inform the research objectives and contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the field. This research article follows structure to ensure a complete review of the literature. It begins by providing an overview of the research topic and its significance, highlighting its relevance in the broader context of the field.

The proportion of people residing in urban areas rose from 27 percent in 1991 to 43 percent in 2011. Namibia is experiencing rapid urbanisation, as evident from the 2011 Census, which reveals that more than 900,000 people, constituting 43% of the total population, reside in urban areas; this marks a significant increase from 33% recorded in 2001 (Namibia Statistics Agency, 2015).

Katima Mulilo is where most of the migration from rural Zambezi region is concentrated. The Namibia Statistics Agency forecasted that the population of Katima Mulilo would reach 50, 000 individuals by 2030, assuming the current growth rate continues trend continues (Namibia Statistics Agency, 2015). Katima Mulilo serves as Namibia's primary economic centre, of the Zambezi region contributing to over 20% of the nation's manufacturing activity (Pendelton & Crush 2014). The town has a distinctive modern and thriving central business activities which attracts migrants to enhance livelihoods. As a result urban population is expected to increase dramatically while the rural population is expected to gradually shrink. According to Pendelton (2014) it is established that only 30% of the total household population in Katima Mulilo are born there, of which the majority is considered to be youth. It is important to note is that the majority of Katima Mulilo migrants settle in the town's rapidly growing and underserviced informal settlements (Pendleton & Crush, 2014). Additionally, Pendleton and Crush (2014) narates the following:

There are several significant migration streams to Katima Mulilo, Namibia. The primary stream is internal migration, particularly rural-urban migration from all coners of the Zambezi region of Namibia. This stream constituted 30% of Katima Mulilo's total population in 2011 and accounted for 50% of the migrant population. Within this internal migration stream, migrants from all corners of the Zambezi, namely Kongla, Kabbe, Sagwali, Chichimani, Mayuni and Bukalo, represented 38% of the migrants. Furthermore, migrants originating from the other regions such as, Kavango East and West regions contributed an additional 8% to the overall migrant population.

The distribution of the Namibian population varies significantly due to regional disparities arising from differences in environmental conditions and historical factors (Pendelton & Crush, 2014). Drought in the country is one of the environmental aspects leading to migration (Pendelton & Crush, 2014). Ajaero (2013) explains that the act of people migrating to different regions in search of improved livelihoods is not a recent phenomenon. Nevertheless, what has gained momentum is the enhanced rate at which low-skill workers and unemployed population is moving from rural areas to urban areas. People move due to the percived real opportunities linked to rural-urban inequality wealth (Ajaero, 2013).

. By embracing a holistic approach, the complexities of urbanisation can be navigated to forge pathways that harmonize different aspects for the benefit of urban communities (Niva *et al.*, 2019)

II.I. PULL AND PUSH FACTORS FOR MIGRANTS

Improved employment openings in urban areas is one of the main reasons reported why migrants leave place of origin while other migrant indicated that their departure is because of poverty (Eshetu & Beshir, 2017). states that determinants that influence rural-urban migration are attributed to dispossession of traditional land, lack of employment opportunities in rural areas and worsening livelihoods. Economists deliberate that internal migration is mainly triggered by differences in the labour markets in the rural and urban areas whereby higher incomes in the urban areas are mostly the pull factors (Selod & Shilpi, 2021). Selod and Shilpi (2021) further explained that past studies mainly focused on migration as a response of labour market condition yet the realization today is that migration is not solely driven by income. However, Eshetu and Beshir (2017) describes that population pressure is also identified to have a contribution towards rural-urban migration because the majority of Africa's population resides in rural regions. As a result, supporting family members in rural areas becomes challenging. As a result many people migrate to live by themselves for an improved livelihood different from the one when with their big extended families in the rural areas (Eshetu & Beshir, 2017).

II.II. DEMOGRAPHIC MAKEUP OF MIGRANTS

Eshetu and Beshir (2017) explains that educated and young individuals are more engaged in migration and as a result it is also established that the majority of migrants are mostly unmarried individuals. Eshetu and Beshir (2017) further reasons that additional factors contributing to the likelihood of unmarried and young individuals leaving rural areas include their pursuit of better job prospects in urban areas, the search for higher education opportunities, entrepreneurial aspirations, a desire to escape restrictive cultural norms, and access to urban amenities and services.

II.III. CHALLENGES OF RURAL-URBAN MIGRATION

Rapid rural-urban migration has a detrimental impact on the availability of infrastructure, housing, and basic services, leading to financial and operational challenges for the responsible local authorities (Tacoli, 2015). It also causes crowding and congestion in urban areas which creates problems for other urban residents. According to the literature, urbanisation leads to various consequences such as a significant housing shortage, rising rental prices, and increased land value within the town. These factors contribute to the spread and growth of numerous informal settlements on the outskirts of urban areas. Urbanisation often results in haphazard and unplanned development, changes in land use patterns, disregard for planning guidelines, inadequate amenities and infrastructure, and the emergence of slum-like conditions (Nwalusi et al, 2022).

Tacoli (2015) elaborates that migrants constitute a significant portion of the urban poor and encounter challenges such as securing adequate housing and accessing essential services. Additionally, they are subjected to low-paid, insecure and unsafe employment which minimizes their potential of accessing basic services (Tacoli, 2015). moreover, they are exposed to a wide range of environmental hazards because informal settlements lack basic infrastructure which puts them at a disadvantage to be affected by these hazards. Urbanisation in developing countries is mostly driven by rural–urban migration (Okhankhuele & Opafunso, 2013). This has significant economic and social impacts on migrants as well the inhabitants of the particular urban area population (Okhankhuele & Opafunso, 2013)..

II.IV. INFORMAL SETTLEMENTS AND URBANISATION

In many African countries, urbanisation has led to swift and uncontrolled urban expansion, giving rise to housing issues and the emergence of informal settlements (Teye, 2018). In certain African townships, more than half of the population resides in informal settlements, where they face challenges such as limited access to water, inadequate sanitation facilities, and insecure living conditions (Teye, 2018). Informal settlements are rapidly expanding in developing countries where migrants are exposed to poor housing, lack of facilities and infrastructure (Liu & Jia, 2021). Subsequently, it is observed that the biggest development challenge and the the lack of a comprehensive and successful national initiative to tackle the growth of informal settlements is evident in the rapid growth of such settlements (Mendelson, 2017).

Migrants express being dismayed at the overcrowded and unsanitary living conditions found in urban informal settlements and how it affects well-being (Njwambe, Cocks, & Vetter, 2019). Nevertheless, individuals still feel compelled to migrate to dire circumstances as they perceive no viable alternative (Pickbourn, 2018). Majority of the migrants live in informal settlements or backyard shacks, describing the environment and living conditions as limited and congested (Njwambe, *et al.*, 2019).

II.V. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Many people leave rural areas hoping to acquire employment, better basic services and educational facilities which lacks in rural areas (Mlambo, 2018).

Eshetu & Beshir (2017) explains that the trend of rural-urban migration has been on the increase over the years as a result studies have made use of descriptive models to examine the characteristics and determinants of migration. Given the arguments by scholars, this paper attempt to fill a knowledge area by discussing the existing migrants' status quo in the town of Katima Mulilo with particular emphasis to why they migrate and the impact it has on their livelihoods. Due to the alarming rate of rural-urban migration, present studies are focused on studying characteristics and determinants of migrants using descriptive research methods (Eshetu & Beshir, 2017).

Tumwesigye *et al.*, (2021) explains that the decision to migrate can be made by household hence, migration is considered as collective household decision. Furthermore, literature in this field rely extensively on secondary data as a means of collecting relevant and required information relating to rural-urban migration (Okhankhuele & Opafunso, 2013). Because the phenomena of rural-urban migration are highly descriptive with a qualitative research approach is mostly utilised during most studies (Tacoli, 2015). This is to put into the context of understanding the underlying concepts and assumptions behind rural-urban migration to enable a better understanding of the causes and implications of those growing problem of urbanisation. Eshetu and Beshir (2017) Emphasises that qualitative research makes use of methods such as participant observation which results in a narrative descriptive explanation of a setting or practice. Numerous researchers have attempted to comprehend the concept of rural-urban migration on informal settlements although some of this information may not widely speak directly to the provision of rural-urban migration in Namibia.

Urbanisation undoubtedly contributes to the success and failure of development both at the national and regional levels because there is a strong relationship between migration and development and migration is the reason for increasing spatial inequality (Marta *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, migration is considered a problem that burdens development and the uncertainty of the benefit gained from migration has not been clearly articulated. As a result, households in the rural areas are experiencing negative economic shocks as people migrate to urban areas to acquire better livelihoods.

III. METHODS

The exploratory and case study research designs and the qualitative research method was particularly relevant for this study on rural-urban migration due their ability to explore the complexities, perspectives, and circumstantial factors associated with migration. The exploratory, qualitative research design emphasises capturing the abundance and depth of human experiences. By employing qualitative methods such as interviews and observations, this study was able to explore the difficulties and challenges faced by migrants during the process of rural-urban migration.

It allowed the researcher gain understanding into the multifaceted factors that influence individuals' decisions to migrate. This also encompassed social and economic aspects. Through in-depth interviews using non-structured questions, participants had the opportunity to share their personal stories, aspirations, and the impact of migration on their lives. This participant-centred approach facilitated a nuanced understanding of the lived experiences of migrants and shed light on the social and economic dimensions of migration.

Furthermore, the qualitative research method provided the flexibility needed to adapt the research focus and explore emergent themes and issues that arose during data collection and analysis. This adaptability allowed the researcher to capture the diverse

dimensions of rural-urban migration, including variations in, experiences and outcomes among different migrants. It also facilitated the exploration of background factors, such as socioeconomic conditions, that shape migration patterns.

III.I. POPULATION

This study investigated the migrants residing in the Katima Mulilo Urban and Rural Constituencies. The above-mentioned constituencies were identified to establish the situation of rural-urban migration particularly in the informal settlements. The two constituencies, according to the Zambezi Regional Council are where the majority of migrant's flock to, hence, were deemed somewhat representative of other constituencies. The combined population size for the two constituencies amounts to a total population size of 30 210 inhabitants (Zambezi Regional Council, 2022).

III.II. SAMPLE SIZE

Due to data saturation the sample size interviewed amounted to 30 respondents. A. Rijnsoever (2017) explains that there are no rules in qualitative sampling and that guidelines for judging sample size are often implicit. Qualitative research is mostly an interpretivist endeavour which requires flexible creative thinking and experience.

The process of obtaining a sample for this study involved deliberately selecting respondents who could offer pertinent and comprehensive insights into the research objectives and questions. The aim was to capture the perspectives and experiences of individuals capable of shedding light on the phenomenon of rural-urban migration.

III.III. DATA ANALYSIS

The research paper used a combination of narrative analysis and thematic analysis to examine the collected data and extract meaningful findings. Thematic analysis involved grouping similar content into concepts and themes to identify patterns and relationships within the data. This systematic approach facilitated the quantification of relationships among different content categories.

Narrative analysis was employed to delve into the stories and personal narratives shared by the participants, offering a profound understanding of their perspectives and experiences regarding rural-urban migration. Through a careful analysis of these narratives, the researcher uncovered underlying themes, motivations and emotions that influenced the participants' migration decisions and experiences. This qualitative exploration through narrative analysis added depth to the study.

III.IV. CREDIBILITY

Ultimately, according to Mohajan (2018), credibility may involve the construction of a truthful value accessed from research results positioned in respondents' environmental surroundings. In essence, data validation processes were utilized in order to advance the credibility of the data's truthful value, which enabled the coordination of triangulation, member reviewing, reflective journaling, and peer-examination techniques (Mohajan, 2018). Henceforth, peer-debriefing and data collection procedures aligned with the formulation of peer networks were used to discover multiple opinions that could have significantly enhanced the interpretation of data acquired through transparent and accountable research processes.

III.V. TRANSFERABILITY

In contrast, transferability refers to the procedures that can establish transmittable channels, which may necessitate the conveyance of research specifications and results to various diverse contextual situations. Indeed, researchers transferred data, which may have provided collection procedures that necessitated the discovery of sufficient information that was assimilated into updated and diverse research contexts within diverse research environments (Nicolas, 2021). Meanwhile, corresponding with Morris and Burkett in Mohajan (2018), transferability may have enabled research results to be easily accessed and transferable across various conditions and situations.

III.VI. DEPENDABILITY

Dependability may be the quantification of various systems and product fitness, which can essentially advance analysis processes and techniques so as to enhance data collection, emerging themes, classifications, models, and analytic notifications (Janis, 2022). Meanwhile, the researcher has utilized evaluative techniques incorporated with relevant themes or concepts, which essentially assessed the reliability of respondents' beliefs and emotions associated with the installation of renewable energy mechanisms

IV. FINDINGS

IV.I. ACCESS TO EDUCATION

Education is also a significant concern for migrants living in informal settlements. Migrants may face challenges enrolling their children in school, and those who do enroll may struggle to keep up with their studies due to poor living conditions. Noise pollution, lack of basic amenities, alcohol and drug abuse is identified as the biggest contributing factors that hinder the attendance and progress of children in the informal settlements.

Financial constraints have also been identified as a contributing factor that hinders parents from ensuring that their children stay in school. The implication of the lack of education increases the migrants' children's chances of being unemployable which further results in social exclusion. It is however, noteworthy that despite the challenges a few university students were identified in the informal settlements and are going through tertiary school despite all odds and challenges experienced. Their motivation is really to enhance their livelihood as per their planned departure plans from their respective places of origin. Overall, the impact of migration on migrants' access to basic services in informal settlements is significant.

This study presents the results and discussion of this study delving into the findings. The research paper provides an in-depth analysis of the data collected from participants. The discussion encompasses the multifaceted factors that influence individuals' decisions to migrate, including social and economic aspects. It examines the impact of rural-urban migration on the livelihoods of migrants, shedding light on the difficulties they face and the opportunities they seek in urban areas. The paper provides a platform for in-depth discussion and analysis of the findings. It contributes to the understanding of migration dynamics and highlights the importance of considering social, economic, and contextual factors in addressing the challenges and opportunities associated with rural-urban migration.

IV.II. DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MIGRANTS

This part of the results focuses on exploring the demographic characteristics of the migrants. The latter through examining factors such as age, gender, marital status, educational background, and employment status of the migrants. Basically, understanding how the aforementioned characteristics influence migrant experiences, needs, and livelihoods in the context of rural-urban migration.

IV.III. FACTORS ATTRACTING THE MIGRATION OF INDIVIDUALS FROM RURAL-AREAS TO TOWNS

Focusing on the analysis of investigating the factors that motivate individuals to migration from rural areas to urban areas of Katima Mulilo. The latter through exploration of various variables that play a crucial role in attracting rural inhabitants, such as economic opportunities, access to services, improved infrastructure, and the influence of climate change.

IV.IV. THE EFFECT OF MIGRATION ON THE WELL-BEING AND EXPERIENCES OF MIGRANTS REGARDING ACCESS TO BASIC SERVICES

The investigation focuses on the consequences of migration on the migrants' access to basic services. Further exploring the challenges faced by migrants in terms of accessing basic services such as education, healthcare, water, sanitation, and electricity.

The analysis further explores the disparities and limitations migrants encounter in informal settlements, where inadequate provision of the aforementioned services often prevails.

THE DEMOGRAPHIC TRAITS OF THE MIGRATING POPULATION

AGE AND GENDER

Table 4. 1 Age and Gender

Age-Group	Female	Male	Grand Total
10– 20	2	5	7
21 – 30	15	16	31
31 – 40	10	6	16
50 – 56	2	6	10
Grand Total	29	33	74

The table above provides detailed information on migrant ages, gender distribution, and the correlations between these factors, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the demographics of the migrant population.

The study conducted encompassed a wide range of age groups. The study revealed that a significant proportion of migrants are young adults aged between 10 and 20. This is an age group that constitutes the majority of migrants, accounting for 46 percent of the total population interviewed for the study. The fact that almost half of the migrant population falls within this age range indicates a preference for migration among individuals in their late twenties to mid-thirties. Moreover, the study found that 40 percent of the migrants interviewed were male, while the remaining 60 percent were female. Gender plays a significant role in shaping the migration process, and analyzing these differences can help develop targeted policies and support systems to address the specific requirements of both genders.

In contrast, the age group between 10 and 20 is more inclined to migrate due to family-related reasons or in pursuit of better educational opportunities. This indicates that younger individuals often move with their families or seek educational advancement in new locations. Hence, the circumstances surrounding migration are diverse and encompass various groups, including children, families, and older adults seeking improved living conditions. The motivations and needs of migrants vary significantly based on age and family circumstances.

LEVEL OF EDUCATION

Table 4. 2 Migrant level of education

Qualification	10– 22	23 - 30	35 – 40	45 – 50	Grand Total
Bachelors/Honors Degree	1	3			4
Bachelors/Honour's degree	2	1	1	2	6
Grade 1 – 7		3		4	7
Grade 8 – 12	3	31	8	7	49
No Education					
Postgraduate		4			4
Vocational/Technical education		3			3
Grand Total	6	45	9	13	73

The table above presents detailed information on the qualifications of migrants and how they correlate with different age groups. The educational background of migrants displays significant variation. Some migrants possess higher levels of education, as they seek opportunities for professional growth and specialised employment in urban areas. On the other hand, the majority of migrants interviewed have lower levels of education, typically ranging from grade 8 to 12. These individuals migrate in pursuit of employment in low-skilled or informal sectors, with the aim of improving their living standards. Notably, those with the lowest level of education are primarily concentrated within the age groups of 23-30 and 35-40. This finding suggests that the majority of migrants belong to the working-age population, characterized by a lower level of educational attainment, specifically within the grade 8-12 category. This implies that a significant proportion of migrants are individuals who are actively participating in the labor force and seeking employment opportunities. Understanding the relationship between educational qualifications and age groups among migrants provides valuable insights into the dynamics of the migrant population.

MOVE EXPECTATIONS

Figure 1. 1 Move expectations

The findings of the study reveal that a significant portion of migrants, specifically 40 percent, expressed that their move to Katima Mulilo did not meet their initial expectations. On the other hand, 50 percent of the migrants reported that their expectations were indeed fulfilled by their relocation. These expectations varied among individuals and encompassed a wide range of aspirations, including starting a business, attaining improved living standards, accessing education, and securing employment.

LIVING CONDITIONS**Figure 4. 2. Living Condition difference**

The findings indicate that a substantial percentage, 72 percent, of the migrants interviewed reported a negative impact on their living conditions after moving to urban areas. Migrants stressed that the cost of living in rural areas is more affordable compared to the Katima Mulilo cost of living. They further stressed that in some instances rural areas where they originate from provides better access to basic services such as water, electricity, and sanitation facilities particularly so when compared to the informal settlements in Katima Mulilo. However, despite the benefits in rural areas, there are certain basic amenities that are not readily available in the rural areas. Nonetheless, the primary reason for migrants choosing to stay in urban areas is their ability to be self-sufficient and not be dependent on others.

Although the living conditions are not ideal, they are able to provide for themselves without relying on external support. This emphasises the importance of independence and self-sustainability for some migrants, outweighing the challenges they face in the Windhoek informal settlements.

IV.V. FACTORS ATTRACTING THE MOVEMENT OF PEOPLE

Due to high levels of poverty, limited job opportunities, and lack of or limited basic services in rural areas migrants shared that they to Katima Mulilo in search of improved livelihoods and more economic opportunities. Most of the migrants had a perception that the quality of life is better in urban areas due to factors such as improved access to employment opportunities, basic services, improved living standards, enhanced educational opportunities, and a broader range of social benefits. This perception of an enhanced quality of life is what motivated most to move in search of a better standard of living.

IV.VI. FAMILY TIES IN URBAN AREAS

Another aspect or basis of moving to urban areas, people indicated that they have friends, relatives, or acquaintances in the city who provide them with information, assistance and places to relocate upon their move. It is established that the majority of migrants come and stay with relatives when they come to Katima Mulilo. However, there is a small number that indicated that they come and reside with their friends until they are able to get on their feet. These existing networks facilitate the transition and integration process, making the move to urban areas more appealing. It is, noteworthy that upon the migrants move to urban areas for those whose initial plan was to acquire opportunities it has come to their realization that the ability to seek opportunities to better their livelihoods is not as simple as alleged. For those that came because of invitation or because of parents moving, the

realization overtime was that enhancing their livelihood became a prerequisite after the understanding that life in the capital city is not as per the initial perception of what their expectations of life in urban areas.

IV.VII. MIGRANTS MIGRATION EXPECTATIONS

Migrants typically perceived Katima Mulilo to offer better infrastructure such as reliable basic amenities, well-maintained roads, and improved housing options. The latter and the perceived availability of the basic amenities and infrastructure is what attracts individuals seeking for a higher standard of living and improved living conditions. The migrants alluded to the fact that the above is somewhat incorrect. The missing piece of information was that it is not applicable to the rest of in town mostly in the informal settlement. After relocation migrants allude to the fact that, although Katima Mulilo has better infrastructure and basic services the experience for those residing in the informal settlements of Katima Mulilo is different. The latter is given the informal set-up of the informal settlements. This realisation became evident upon arrival to Katima Mulilo the migrants narrated.

The absence of basic services particularly water supply, ablution facilities, refuse disposal and electricity immediately became evident. Furthermore, on observation and discussion the informal settlements are so informal that there are no proper road networks, which hinders the transportation of the sick residents promptly to the nearby health facilities. Due to the limited and lack of the aforementioned, informal settlements in Katima Mulilo are characterised by poor living conditions and limited infrastructure, which has a significant implication on the health and well-being of migrants who reside in these settlements. It is further observed that infrastructure challenges that migrants in informal settlements are exposed to include overcrowding, whereby large numbers of people live in small and poorly constructed corrugated iron sheets as houses also referred to as shacks. This definitely increases the risk of the spread of infectious diseases, as well as contribute to mental health issues such as stress and anxiety where people in the areas are now involving themselves in criminal activities, abuse of alcohol and drugs and committing to gender-

V. DISCUSSIONS

This section provides results analysed and interpreted based on the data gathered from sample respondents within the Katima Mulilo Urban and Rural constituencies. Key respondents were interviewed through a prepared questionnaire focusing on the socio-demographic characteristics of migrants, causes of rural-urban migration and its consequence for migrants at the place of destination.

DEMOGRAPHICS

Understanding the demographics of migrant populations provided valuable insights into migrant motivations, experiences, and the broader impact of migration at their urban area destination. Demographic aspects of rural-urban migration, have insights into the factors that influence migration decisions and the composition of migrant populations, and the implications. One of the distinct demographic characteristics of migrants is that they are mostly young adults. Delango (2019) explains that age is one of the factors that influence the young age groups migrate because the young groups seems to be less satisfied with the rural agricultural system and are more ambitious to test urban life.

The elderly mostly move for access to better healthcare and offspring care provision. Although young adults form most of the migrants' population the majority of them tend to be unemployed. High unemployment among migrants is attributed to the prevalence of low level of education and lack of specialised skills prevalent among migrants. Notable is also that there are trends and aspects about migrants, such as most of the young migrants being unmarried and high unemployment rates amongst them. Young people are more likely to be engaged in rural-urban migration because of their flexibilities to migrate. They often seek employment, business opportunities, education, and a more a better social environment.

Migrants' decision to migrate is also influenced by marital status. Various literature states that people who have no family obligation are more inclined to move (Delango, 2019). Thus, those that have no family ties are more likely to migrate from their place origin to urban areas with better economic opportunities (Delango, 2019). There is a growing trend of more unmarried people migrating. Factors such as the desire for independence and the pursuit of personal aspirations influence unmarried

individuals to migrate. Their flexibility and less commitments make them more motivated to seek better opportunities or personal growth in urban area.

LIVING CONDITION OF MIGRANTS

The rising cost of living in urban areas poses a challenge for migrants. Inflationary pressures further intensify the cost of living for migrants in informal settlements as the increasing cost of goods and services increasingly makes it difficult for migrants to afford their daily necessities. Due to inflation purchasing power of the consumer (s) is reduced, thus affecting consumer consumption patterns and ultimately affecting livelihoods. Brandt (2022) Explains that increasing prices in fuel, electricity, food and transport in the absence of employment and salary increments for the majority of Namibian employees pushes down the purchasing power for the ordinary Namibian. Brandt (2022) further explained that the increasing commodity prices causing high inflation will push Namibian citizens into poverty and increase the economic hardship that is already existing.

It is undeniable that housing, transportation, and basic necessities such as sanitation water and electricity tend to be more expensive in cities. More so because migrants are already struggling to acquire employment and income generating opportunities. Although the goal of migration was to acquire better prospects, lack of employment and income generating opportunities remain a prevalent issue among rural-urban migrants. Many individuals migrate in the hope of finding employment but struggle to secure jobs in urban areas.

VI. AREAS FOR FUTURE STUDIES

Although existing literature provided perspectives on numerous characteristics of rural-urban migration, there are still some areas that warrant further investigation. Some of the potential areas for future research on rural-urban migration include:

- Examining the effects of rural-urban migration on rural communities, focusing on the economic consequences of rural-urban migration on rural economies, particularly on the impact it has on agriculture, social structures and the well-being of those who remain in rural areas. How can rural areas be economically elevated to enhance local economies to mitigate migration?
- Examine the health and well-being of migrants in urban areas, accessing healthcare services, exposure to health risks, and the social determinants of health, particularly in the informal settlements, especially given their poor living conditions and limited access to basic services delivery.
- Investigate how climate change and environmental factors influence migration decisions. Focusing on the relationship between climate change and rural-urban migration, how environmental factors, such as drought and resource scarcity in the rural areas, influence migration decisions and shape the susceptibility and flexibilities of migrants in urban areas. Concentrating on the aforementioned proposed areas, future studies can contribute to a more enhanced understanding of rural-urban migration, its implications, and prospective strategies for addressing the challenges and linking the opportunities associated with rural-urban migration.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The key findings from the research paper shed light on the multifaceted factors driving rural-urban migration, the challenges migrants face in accessing basic services, and the demographic characteristics of migrants. These findings underscore the critical importance of addressing these issues to ensure sustainable and inclusive urban development. The factors attracting individuals from rural areas to urban centers, particularly in the case of Katima Mulilo include economic opportunities, access to essential services, improved infrastructure, and the growing influence of climate change. The pursuit of better economic prospects, facilitated by enhanced employment opportunities and entrepreneurial possibilities, emerges as a primary driver of rural-urban migration.

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